

Agrivoltaics on Mahé (Seychelles): A first potential analysis based on an acceptance study

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Introduction to the study

The world's energy markets are constantly changing. There is a need for a transformation in the way energy is produced and consumed, which becomes clear in the Paris Climate Agreement. It has set the goal of limiting global warming to 1.5 degrees compared to pre-industrial levels; this requires worldwide net-zero emissions by 2050. Furthermore, due to recent events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the war between Russia and Ukraine, an increase in energy prices has been seen which, in turn, has led to some countries aiming for new targets and policies to increase the share of renewable energies. In addition, the awareness of the effects of climate change has increased due to the effects of extreme weather events worldwide (IRENA, 2023; REN21, 2023).

Tropical countries are experiencing an increase in energy demand due to socio-economic changes. In one such tropical country, Seychelles, electricity demand is expected to increase and reach 875 GWh/a by 2030. This makes it important to consider renewable energy sources at an early stage to meet this increase and take into account the goals of the Paris Climate Agreement (Brown et al., 2016; IRENA, 2023; Sulaiman, 2021).

As a Small Island Development State (SIDS), Seychelles faces particular challenges. This is due to the characteristic features of SIDS which include remoteness, small size, and dependency on imports. Climate change in particular is a major threat to Seychelles, especially in the agricultural sector. Due to a high proportion of imports in the agricultural sector, but also in the energy sector and the resulting vulnerability, it is very important to promote independence from external influences. Seychelles has set the goal of achieving a net-zero emission economy by 2050. In this context, agrivoltaics could also be an approach to promote energy security and food security (Brown et al., 2016; FAO and ICRISAT, 2019; Republic of Seychelles, 2021; Trommsdorff et al., 2022; UN-OHRLLS, 2020).

There is currently little research on agrivoltaics in Seychelles. In March 2024, a workshop with the title *Technology Assessment of Agrivoltaics for Controlled-environment Crop Production* was held by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development in Seychelles. The workshop was implemented as part of the project promoting technology assessment in the agricultural and energy sectors in Africa and aims to bring stakeholder perspectives into the project (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2024a and 2024b).

This study aims to contribute to filling the gap in research on agrivoltaics in the tropical island state of Seychelles, and to form a foundation for a successful implementation of agrivoltaics. It deals with the potential analysis of agrivoltaics with a special focus on an acceptance study.

Objective of the investigation

In this study, Seychelles is considered an exemplary country in the tropics; and a potential analysis is carried out with a focus on an acceptance study. Acceptance (see next section on research methodology) is defined here as a positive or tolerant way to view, respond or act towards a new technology or product or to normative regulations and standards. In this context, acceptance research examines the willingness to accept innovations and, in this case, the technology of agrivoltaics. The term potential (see next section) is defined in this study as the possibility through technology for further development and its introduction and establishment into a new context; and this includes the direction of further research and the identification of further approaches. Acceptance in this context is an integral part of the potential.

According to the current state of knowledge, agrivoltaics have not yet been implemented or successfully realized in Seychelles. Farmers have a central role in the successful integration of agrivoltaics in Seychelles. For this reason, the focus of this study is on farmers. The objective of the study is to gain insights into the acceptance and perception of Seychellois farmers towards agrivoltaics. The data collection in the study aims to identify the familiarity towards agrivoltaics, and the barriers and opportunities that farmers see in the implementation of the technology. It also aims to determine the openness of the farmers towards the implementation of agrivoltaics on their farms and the possible support options and further steps needed to increase the willingness of the farmers. Another goal is to determine the characteristics of the farms to identify the differences between the farms and possible potentials in connection with agrivoltaics.

Research methodology

The data material for the following study was collected from 76 personal surveys of farmers on Mahé. The thematic focus of the research will be on overhead and interspace systems for crop cultivation. One survey result was not included in the analysis, as 100% livestock farming was stated here. The approach of the study can be divided into sub-steps. The first step consisted of expert interviews, followed by the creation of the surveys and a pre-test. After the evaluation, the surveys were finalized and carried out. This was followed by the analysis of the results.

The term ‘potential’ can have different meanings in different fields. In this study, potential refers to the possibilities of the technology for its further development and its introduction and establishment in a new context. This includes the directions in which future research could develop, as well as the identification of possible approaches. Acceptance is seen as an integral part of the potential, as it includes the farmers' perspectives on the technology. The focus of the potential analysis in this paper is therefore on an acceptance study to investigate the acceptance of agrivoltaics among farmers in Seychelles. To enable this, and to gain insights into the current challenges and requirements for the farmers, the chosen method for data collection was survey research. To ensure the reachability of the survey, personal interviews with participants were carried out. The survey questionnaire was divided into four main sections. These are: *Perception of Agrivoltaics*, *Support Offers and Integration of Agrivoltaics*, *Characteristics of the Farm* and *Demographic Background*. A combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods was chosen.

The Likert scale type as a five-, seven-, and ten-point scale, is used in surveys to measure the subjective attitude of participants towards certain topics. The Likert scale enables the respondent's attitude towards a certain ‘latent’ variable to be queried. For this purpose, items are used that each represents a dimension of the phenomenon and, in their entirety, can provide conclusions about the topic as a whole. With the Likert scale, on the other hand, the individual questions of a topic are analysed independently of each other (Joshi et al., 2015). For the survey, a 5-point scale was chosen. In addition, the majority of the questions are a Likert scale type, as they cannot provide a comprehensive picture of the topic and further aspects can be added.

The first section *Perception* includes familiarity with the technology, the barriers and opportunities that farmers see in the implementation of the technology on their farms and the consideration of implementing. The familiarity aims to identify the extent to which the farmers are already familiar with the topic of agrivoltaics at the beginning of the survey, using a scale from ‘not familiar’ (1) to ‘very familiar’ (5). Subsequently, eleven barriers (see Table 1) are examined, using a Likert type scale ranging from ‘not a barrier’ (1), to ‘a slight barrier’ (2), to ‘a moderate barrier’ (3), to ‘a barrier’ (4) and to ‘a major barrier’ (5). The questionnaire then examines thirteen predefined opportunities (see Table 1), using a Likert type scale ranging from ‘not an opportunity’ (1), to ‘a slight opportunity’ (2), to ‘a moderate opportunity’ (3), to ‘an opportunity’ (4) and to ‘a major opportunity’ (5). The selection of the barriers and opportunities examined is based on the expert interviews, experiences from the pre-tests, Trommsdorff et al. (2022), Public Utilities Corporation (n.d.-a), U.S. Department of Energy (2022), and information and experiences gained from personal conversations. The *Support Offers and Integration of Agrivoltaics* section (see Table 1) aims to identify the required support options and next steps. Farmers are asked whether the five listed support offers would increase their willingness to implement agrivoltaics on their farm. This is asked on a five-point scale from ‘no’ (1), to ‘probably not’ (2), to ‘neutral’ (3), to ‘probably yes’ (4) and to ‘yes’ (5).

Table 1: Barriers, Opportunities and Support Offers analysed in the survey

Source: Own illustration

Barriers	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ Investment costs ◇ Running costs ◇ Long administrative processes for financial support ◇ Maintenance ◇ Lack of specialized knowledge and experts in the field of agrivoltaics ◇ System flexibility (for changing framework, e.g. changing crops) ◇ The suitability for the crops ◇ Limited allowed monthly renewable energy consumption ◇ Energy production fluctuations due to fast changing weather events ◇ Insufficient feed-in tariff ◇ Vandalism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ Dual land use ◇ Shading ◇ Protection of the crops (e.g. from extreme weather events) ◇ Increasing the efficiency (e.g. reducing the consumption of water/fertiliser) ◇ Potential use of rainwater for irrigation ◇ Increasing land productivity (e.g. improving the growing conditions for the crops) ◇ Improving the resilience ◇ Increasing the share of renewable energy ◇ Self-supply of electricity ◇ Reducing the amount of work by automated processes ◇ Cost saving ◇ Increasing the financial yield through the availability of shade and the possible improvement in the growing conditions ◇ Reduce the carbon emissions of the farm
Support Offers	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ Financial support ◇ Access to information ◇ Informational events ◇ Test set-up to investigate the functionality ◇ Technical support options for repairs and maintenance ◇ Availability of trained officers who are familiar with the technology 	

In addition, *Farm Characteristics* are queried. In this context, the sub-items *farmland*, *electricity*, *agricultural products*, *shade houses*, *irrigation* and *heavy rainfall* are addressed. In the subsection *farmland*, the area of the farm, the cultivable share, the slope, and the occurrence of rocks are queried to record topographical characteristics and the scale of the farms. The subsection *electricity* determines whether the farm is already connected to the electricity grid, the monthly electricity demand, the use of a photovoltaic system, the current share of renewable energies in the electricity consumption, and the largest energy consumers on the farm. The aim is to provide an impression of the current electricity supply situation of the farms. The sub-category *agricultural products* queries the share of farmland used for crops and for livestock, the share of crops above four metres, and what kind of crops the farmers would prefer in shaded areas. As no statement can be made about the suitability of specific

crops in this work, the growth height of the cultivated crops was queried to get an impression of whether these are tall-growing crops such as tree crops or whether they are lower-growing crops. A limit of four metres was chosen as a measure. In the expert interviews, the *shade house* was mentioned as a possible area of consideration in relation to agrivoltaics, as there can occur problems with overheating. For this reason, the farmers were asked whether they have shade houses on their farms, how much land they cover and the purpose of the shade houses. The farmers were asked to rate the usefulness of using the generated electricity to reduce the temperature in the shade houses. The last subsection *irrigation and heavy rainfall* examines whether the farm already has an irrigation system and what kind, the current water source of the farm, whether they see heavy rainfall as a threat to their farm, and what measures they have taken against it. The purpose of this section is to determine the potential of irrigation systems included in agrivoltaics. As an additional question, the perception of the threat of climate change to the farm and whether they have taken measures to reduce the effects of climate change is asked on a scale from 'absolutely not' (1) to 'yes absolutely' (5).

The *Demographic Background* is determined with the aim of obtaining an overview of the survey participants and identifying possible correlations with the perception of agrivoltaics. For this purpose, the age, how long the person has worked in the agricultural sector, educational background, and gender of the participant are included in the survey.

In the evaluation of the results, a correlation between consideration and the characteristics familiarity, farmland size, age, gender, educational background and working experience in the agricultural sector, and the perception of heavy rainfall and climate change was carried out with the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient and the Mann-Whitney U-test (nominal data).

With the help and assistance of the extension workers, the participants were selected from the registered farmers and the surveys were conducted. Initially, the aim was to obtain a variance in the size of the participating farms. During the surveys, however, the criterion of availability of the farmers also played a significant role in the selection of participants. In two and a half weeks a total of 76 surveys were carried out. During the survey, the extension workers helped with language barriers and translated the questions if necessary. As it was possible that some farmers were not yet familiar with the technology, a document with technical design and application examples from other countries, as well as the idea of the possible combination of agrivoltaics with shade houses, was shown during the surveys.

Results

This chapter presents the results of the 75 surveys. It is divided thematically into the subsections *Demographic Background*, *Farm Characteristics*, *Perception*, *Support Offers* and *Correlations*. The results of the surveys were analysed using Excel and JASP.

Demographic Background

A look at demographic background makes it possible to develop a deeper understanding of the studied group. Approximately 11% of the participants are female and approximately 89% are male. Of the farmers, 4% are between the ages of 20 and 29, 12% between 30 and 39, approximately 25% between 40 and 49, and approximately 59% were 50 years old or older. Approximately 7% have had work experience in the agricultural sector between 0 and 4 years, approximately 7% between 5 and 9 years, approximately 19% between 10 and 19 years, approximately 21% between 20 and 29 years, approximately 31% between 30 and 39 years and 16% with 40 years or more. Approximately 55% have a post-secondary degree, approximately 31% a secondary degree, approximately 9% a primary degree, 4% no degree, and approximately 1% unknown.

Farm Characteristics

The characteristics of the farms can vary greatly. It is therefore important to take this into account when analysing perception, but also for the wider scope of the potential.

Approximately 89% of the surveyed farms are government owned, 8% are privately owned and approximately 3% are both government and privately owned. The majority of farms, approximately 75%, have an area of less than 1000 m² and approximately 95% of the farms are smaller than 35000 m². Approximately 6% of the farms have flat land, 56% of the farmers stated that the farmland has a slope and the remaining have both. In addition, the occurrence of rocks on agricultural land was also examined. Some farmers made multiple selections. Approximately 15% stated that they have no rocks, 44% that they have a few rocks and 36% that they have areas with a lot of rocks.

The surveyed farms have used, on average, approximately 94% of the farmland for crops and approximately 5% for livestock. Approximately 67% of the crops were under four metres in height and approximately 32% were taller than four metres. The farmers were also asked which crops they would prefer in shaded regions based on their own experience. Lettuce, cabbage, Chinese cabbage, cucumber, and tomatoes were named most frequently. To determine the potential, the current status of the farm's electricity demand is important to look at. Approximately 57% of the surveyed farms were not connected to the electricity grid at the time of the survey and approximately 43% were connected. Many farms have a residential building next to the farm, but this was not covered in this survey. The monthly electricity demand of the connected farms was queried in SCR (Seychelles Rupees) or kWh. The majority of the farms answered this question in SCR. The mean value was

selected for responses in a range. Three farms stated that the electricity consumption was not known, and one farm reported only in kWh and not in SCR. It can be seen that 75% of the farms have an energy consumption of up to 2500 SCR and there are only a few farms with a higher electricity demand.

In addition, the major electric energy consumers of the farms were analysed. A total of twelve different energy consumers were named. Irrigation has been identified as the major electric energy consumer with approximately 59% of the farms, followed by lights, 25%, storage systems, approximately 16%, and pumps with approximately 13%.

Shade houses are used by 16% of the surveyed farmers; approximately 92% of these farmers use the shade houses to protect crops from heavy rainfall, approximately 67% to protect crops from strong irradiation, and approximately 42% to protect crops from pests. The average area of the shade houses is approximately 2,400 m², with the vast majority of shade houses having an area of less than 1,000 m². In addition, the farmers were asked how useful they consider the use of agrivoltaics to reduce the temperature of shade houses. Of the twelve farmers using shade houses, three farmers said 'very useful', four 'useful', one 'moderately useful', and four 'not useful'.

At the time of the survey, approximately 69% of farmers were using an irrigation system on the farm, with a majority (approximately 91%) using water from rivers or streams as a water source. Water from the public water supply and rainwater each accounted for water use on approximately 5% of the farms. Groundwater and water from reservoirs were used on approximately 7%. Some farmers used a water catchment that can supply several farms. This differentiation is not included in the data.

Perception

The following section contains the results of farmers' perceptions towards agrivoltaics, possible support offers, as well as perceptions of heavy rainfall and climate change.

The majority of participants (approximately 71%) stated that they were 'not familiar' with the technology, approximately 17% 'a little familiar', approximately 7% 'moderately familiar', 4% 'familiar', and approximately 1% 'very familiar' with the concept of agrivoltaics before the survey.

Tables 2 and 3 provide an overview of the given barriers and opportunities that were analysed individually. The numbers indicate the number of responses of the individual scale points on the scale from 'not a barrier/opportunity' (1), 'slight barrier/opportunity' (2), 'moderate barrier/opportunity' (3), 'barrier/opportunity' (4), to 'major barrier/opportunity' (5). It should be noted that some farmers were not yet able to give an answer to this question (highlighted in grey). The mean value of the ratings from 1 to 5 is shown in the red (Table 2)/tourquoise column (Table 3). A high mean value indicates a high level of agreement among the surveyed farmers and a low mean value indicates a low

level of agreement. In addition, the scale points with the most responses are coloured red (Table 2)/green (Table 3).

Table 2: Overview of the results of the participants ratings regarding the given barriers

Source: Own illustration

	Not a barrier (1)	Slight barrier (2)	Moderate barrier (3)	Barrier (4)	Major barrier (5)	No answer	Mean
Investment costs	4	1	9	6	54	1	4,42
Running costs	16	5	11	12	25	6	3,36
Long administrative process for financial support	6	2	6	20	37	4	4,13
Maintenance	14	7	9	10	35	0	3,6
Lack of specialized knowledge and experts	6	5	10	19	35	0	3,96
System flexibility	8	4	11	24	25	3	3,75
Suitability for the crops	19	3	13	7	25	8	3,24
Limited allowed monthly renewable energy consumption	18	4	11	17	20	5	3,24
Energy production fluctuations	17	8	13	13	20	4	3,15
Insufficient feed-in tariff	16	6	7	16	21	9	3,30
Vandalism	22	7	7	5	31	3	3,22

The mean value of the barriers examined is between 3.15 and 4.42. The barriers with the highest mean value are: ‘investment costs’. with 4.42; ‘long administrative process for financial support’, with 4.13; and ‘lack of specialized knowledge and experts’ in the field of agrivoltaics, with 3.96. The barriers with the lowest mean value are: ‘energy production fluctuations’, with 3.15; ‘vandalism’, with 3.22; and ‘suitability for the crops’ and ‘limited allowed monthly renewable energy consumption’, with 3.24 each.

Figures 1 and 2 show the distribution of the results of the ratings in a net diagram. The graphical representation in a net diagram offers the possibility to see the barriers and opportunities in relation to each other. The number of ratings is shown from the center to the outside and the corners show the scale points.

Figure 1:
Overview of the results of the participants' ratings regarding the given barriers, in a net diagram

Source: Own illustration

The graphical representation clearly shows that 'investment costs' is the largest of the barriers mentioned. For some of the barriers, the vast majority of responses are only at the higher values of the scale points, such as 'lack of specialized knowledge and experts'. For 'vandalism', on the other hand, the majority of responses include both of the extreme values (1 and 5). And for the 'suitability for the crops' barrier, there is also a focus on the extreme values (1 and 5) and on the middle (3) for moderate barriers.

The survey also asked the open question of what other barriers did the farmers see in the implementation of agrivoltaics on their farms. Approximately 61% of the farmers mentioned more barriers than those listed above. The most frequently mentioned barrier was 'topography' with sixteen mentions. Another important barrier, with nine mentions, is 'lack of information/experience and knowledge'. This also includes the need to upskill workers. Several barriers had five mentions, these are: the 'age' of the survey participants; the 'scale of the farm, different crops necessary, current regulations and policies'; and the 'loan' (e.g. interest, payback time). The 'weather' and the 'general difficult agricultural situation and vulnerability' were mentioned four times. The 'weather' includes wind and heavy rainfall. The dependence on agricultural imports and already high investment costs due to the current challenges were also counted in the 'general difficult agricultural situation and vulnerability'. The 'preference for different or old systems', the 'availability of materials and technology' and the 'profitability/benefits' of the technology were mentioned three times. 'Profitability/benefits' also include the barrier of low electricity demand on farms and the associated need to maximize electricity consumption.

The results of the survey regarding the opportunities that the farmers see in the implementation of agrivoltaics on their farms are shown in Table 3. The mean value of the different opportunities ranges between 3.35 and 4.24. The opportunities perceived most strongly by the farmers are 'self-supply of electricity' and 'reducing the amount of work by automated processes' with a mean value of 4.24 each, and 'cost saving' with 4.23. The lowest opportunities seen by the farmers are 'shading' with a mean value of 3.35, 'dual land use' with 3.63 and 'increasing land productivity' with 3.66.

Table 3: Overview of the results of the participants ratings regarding the given Opportunities

Source: Own illustration

	Not an opportunity (1)	Slight opportunity (2)	Moderate opportunity (3)	Opportunity (4)	Major opportunity (5)	No answer	Mean
Dual land use	8	7	13	24	23	0	3,63
Shading	2	6	10	26	18	13	3,35
Protection of the crops (e.g. extreme weather events)	1	3	13	27	23	8	3,73
Increasing the efficiency (e.g. reducing the consumption of water/fertilizer)	1	5	8	23	29	9	3,78
Potential use of rainwater for irrigation	1	1	6	27	36	4	4,17
Increasing land productivity (e.g. improving the growing conditions for the crops)	2	3	9	23	26	12	3,66
Improving the resilience	0	3	7	28	30	7	3,95
Increasing the share of renewable energy	1	2	14	23	30	5	3,92
Self-supply of electricity	1	2	8	19	42	3	4,24
Reducing the amount of work by automated processes	1	2	9	24	37	2	4,24
Cost saving	0	3	9	19	41	3	4,23
Increasing the financial yield through the availability of shade and possible improvement in the growing condition	0	2	13	19	31	10	3,86
Reduce the carbon emissions of the farm	0	5	6	25	28	11	3,79

Figure 2 shows the results of the survey regarding the listed opportunities in a net diagram. In comparison to the barriers, there is a further focus of the responses on the scale point 'opportunity' (4). A relatively low response rate can be observed in the areas 'not an opportunity' (1), and 'slight opportunity' (2).

Figure 2:
Overview of the results of the participants' ratings regarding the given opportunities, in a net diagram
Source: Own illustration

Farmers were also asked about other opportunities that they see with the implementation of agrivoltaics on their farms. With a total of 26, 32% of the farmers indicated further opportunities. The most frequently mentioned was 'electricity use for the house', with four mentions, and 'selling electricity/feed into the grid', with three mentions. In addition, 'combination with hydroponics' and 'livestock farming' were mentioned twice each.

After looking at the barriers and opportunities, the farmers were asked whether they would consider implementing agrivoltaics on their farms in the future. Of the 75 farmers,

approximately 37% stated they would consider agrivoltaics for their farm, 24% would probably consider agrivoltaics, 20% were neutral on the subject, approximately 15% would not consider and 4% would probably not consider agrivoltaics.

Table 4 shows the correlation of consideration with the various characteristics using Spearman's Rho Coefficient. The results show significant positive correlations between familiarity and consideration as well as between farmland size and consideration. This significance can be explained by the fact that the p-values in this case are smaller than 0.05.

Table 4: Correlations between consideration and different variables collected in the survey using the Spearman's Rho Sample Correlation Coefficient

Source: Own illustration produced with JASP

Spearman's Correlation		Spearman's Rho *p < .05	p
Familiarity	- consideration	0.271*	0.018
Farmland size [m ²]	- consideration	0.238*	0.039
Climate change as a threat	- consideration	0.039	0.738
Age	- consideration	-0.134	0.251
Experience in agric. sector	- consideration	0.030	0.797
Educational background	- consideration	0.087	0.459

The Mann-Whitney U-test between consideration and heavy rainfall as a threat shows no significant results, W=266 p=0.605. No significant results were found between consideration and gender either, W=203 p=0.272.

Farmers were also asked whether they perceive heavy rainfall and climate change as a threat to their farms and 88% stated that they see heavy rainfall as a threat. Approximately 88% of the farmers stated 'yes' (5) or 'probably yes' (4) to the question of whether they perceive climate change as a threat.

Furthermore, it was investigated which support offers would increase the willingness to implement agrivoltaics. The scale of possible answers ranged from 'no' (1), 'probably not' (2), 'neutral' (3), 'probably yes' (4) and 'yes' (5). Figure 3 shows the responses of the farmers based on the predefined scale. It shows that the majority of respondents selected 'yes' (5) for all support offers mentioned. The mean value ranges between 4.39 for 'informational events', to 4.63 for 'test setups to investigate the functionality'. The mean value for 'availability of trained officers who are familiar with the technology' is 4.51; 'access to information' is 4.47; and 'technical support options for repair and maintenance' is 4.44.

Figure 3:
Response distribution on a five-step scale from ‘no’ to ‘yes’ to the question: ‘Would the availability of the following support options increase your willingness to implement agrivoltaics on your farm?’
 Source: Own illustration

Approximately 23% of the farmers surveyed indicated a total of sixteen other support offers that would increase their willingness to implement agrivoltaics. The most frequently mentioned offer with six mentions is ‘training/introduction of the new system’. ‘encouragement’ and ‘simple complete solutions’ were each mentioned twice. ‘Encouragement’ means that an incentive is needed, for example in trials on other farms or larger farms.

Interpretation of results

The aim of the work is to gain insights, through surveys, into the acceptance and perception of farmers in Seychelles, as an exemplary tropical country, and to identify possible potentials in relation to agrivoltaics by identifying possible approaches and further steps regarding the implementation of agrivoltaics. As already indicated in the section on methodology, it is important to investigate the acceptance of stakeholders to introduce new technologies. The results of the survey are presented and interpreted below in the context of the research objectives, the background research, and the current state of research.

The results of the acceptance study show that farmers are open to the technology, and that the majority of farmers would consider agrivoltaics in the future. The results also reveal that familiarity towards agrivoltaics was relatively small at the beginning of the survey. As familiarity has been shown to have a significant positive correlation with the consideration of agrivoltaics, its promotion seems to be an important issue to address. This could be achieved by providing information, and disseminating knowledge about agrivoltaics. In addition, the most frequent mention of other support offers is in ‘training/introduction’ of agrivoltaics. This shows that there is also interest in expanding the knowledge regarding

the implementation of agrivoltaics. Due to the significant positive correlation between the farm scale and the farmers consideration of implementing agrivoltaics, the large farms could be considered as a possible starting point for the introduction of agrivoltaics.

A comparison of opportunities and barriers shows that neither the opportunities, with a mean value between 3.35 and 4.24, nor the barriers, with a mean value between 3.15 and 4.42, are predominant. Looking at the distribution of the results with the net diagrams, it becomes clear that there are individual barriers that emerge as a 'major barrier' (5), whereas a more even distribution can be seen for the opportunities. For the opportunities examined, it can be observed that the responses are predominantly in the 'moderate opportunity' (3) to 'major opportunity' (5) range and not focused on the extreme scale points. The evenly distributed response to the opportunities could be based on the fact that there is currently no experience nor practical examples in Seychelles, which would allow farmers to draw conclusions for their own farms. The situation is different for the barriers, where there are a few that receive a noticeably higher weighting and have a focus on the two extreme values of 'not a barrier' (1) and 'major barrier' (5). The differences in the results of the barriers could be based on the fact that the farms have different types of farming activities and different farm characteristics; for example 'vandalism' might happen more in populated areas, and the different cultivated crops could influence the responses regarding the 'suitability of agrivoltaics for the crops'. A comparison of the results of the open-ended question about other barriers and opportunities regarding the implementation of agrivoltaics, which the farmers mentioned, shows that significantly more other barriers (twice as high) were mentioned than other opportunities.

The greatest barrier is 'investment costs'. To overcome this barrier, financing concepts could be considered, for example subsidies. One suggestion would be the promotion of agritourism, where agriculture is combined with tourism. This would make it possible to create awareness of local food production and financially support the farms. Another concept that could be included is a kind of monetary levy or voluntary donations to support local agriculture. In the area of opportunities, however, 'cost-saving' received the second-highest score. For this reason, cost saving can also be seen as an opportunity to reduce costs in the long term. It is useful to do a cost/profitability analysis and therefore determine the amortization period of the system and thus provide farmers with a better basis for decision-making. The study suggests that there is a need for further research in this area.

The most frequently mentioned other barrier is 'topography' with sixteen mentions. In the surveys it was revealed that approximately 6% of the farms have flat land, 36% of the farms have areas with a lot of rocks and 44% have areas with a few rocks. This shows that topography in particular could be a barrier. Further studies would be needed to investigate the extent to which the installation is dependent on the soil and terrain characteristics to determine the individual feasibility for the farms.

'Dual land use' has the second lowest value of the mean values at 3.63. And the most frequent number of responses is at the scale point 'opportunity' (4). This could indicate that, from the farmers' perspective in Seychelles, dual land use does bring an advantage, but is not the main focus for the farmers. Following 'dual land use', the aspect of 'increasing land productivity' was rated third lowest with a mean value of 3.66. Although the farmers do not see any major opportunities in these two aspects, it should still be noted that the LER (land equivalent ratio) in tropical regions is 1.5 according to Gomez-Casanovas et al. (2023) and is higher than in temperate regions. But Seychelles is only a small country in the tropics and therefore probably needs to be considered separately and the LER analysed in future research.

The literature points out that the shading that agrivoltaics can bring can be seen as positive (for example the positive effects of shading on Chicory as mentioned by Semeraro et al. (2024) in Italy). In the evaluation of the survey, 'shading' as an opportunity had the lowest mean value. One could assume that the crops cultivated in the Seychelles would require relatively more direct sunlight than the crops used for the study in Italy. The results of the survey question on what kind of crops farmers would prefer in shaded areas, show that lettuce, cabbage, chinese cabbage, cucumber and tomatoes are among the crops that could benefit from shading by agrivoltaics. Clear differences in the perceptions of the farmers could be seen regarding the 'suitability for the crops', as the majority of responses were on the scale points 'not a barrier' (1) and 'major barrier' (5). Two different effects could be discussed here. On the one hand, the results could indicate that some of the crops currently grown in the Seychelles, as a tropical country, are not ideal for the use of agrivoltaics. It must also be considered that a proportion of approximately 32% of the crops is above four metres and may already be unsuitable due to their growth form as tree crops. On the other hand, these results could also suggest that agrivoltaics in combination with shading could enable farmers to cultivate other crops that they are not yet able to grow.

The composition of the sample of survey participants can have an influence on the results of the survey. The majority of the survey participants are 50 years old or older (approximately 59%) and have worked in the agricultural sector for more than twenty years (68%). Based on the results of the correlation age and work experience in the agricultural sector this does not appear to have an influence on the farmers' consideration nor on the acceptance of agrivoltaics. However, 'age' was mentioned five times as a barrier, which means that age can still be seen as a challenge and should not be disregarded.

The results of the farmers' perception showed a rather balanced result of the opportunities and barriers, that were queried from a given list, and the consideration was rated relatively high. From these results, it can be concluded that the farmers' attitude towards agrivoltaics as a technology is positive and an acceptance of the technology is expressed. However, the barriers investigated and mentioned should not be ignored. Specific support for farmers could have a significant influence on their willingness and could increase it.

To investigate the potential, other aspects were also queried in the survey alongside the acceptance study. Possible approaches, further research fields, and the possible next steps are addressed here. Among other things, an analysis of the farm characteristics was carried out, which shows that only approximately 43% of farms are currently connected to the electricity grid. This could lead to two conclusions in addition to the possible self-supply of electricity. Firstly, the aim could be to achieve electrification of the farms, for example to simplify work by automating certain work steps. An irrigation system could also be used as an example here. Another possibility is to feed any surplus electricity into the grid. Achieving a diversification of the income could be considered here. 'The self-supply of electricity and reducing the amount of work by automated processes' ranked second highest in terms of opportunities with a mean value of 4,24. This means that from the farmers' perspective, the use of energy could also be an opportunity for the future-oriented development of the farm.

In an expert interview, it was mentioned that agrivoltaics could bring benefits in connection with shade houses. Shade houses are used by 16% of the surveyed farmers. A total of approximately 92% of these farmers use shade houses for protection against heavy rainfall and approximately 67% against strong irradiation. Since agrivoltaic systems can be built as overhead systems, it is possible to create a kind of shelter effect with the modules. In addition, about 88% of all farmers surveyed indicated heavy rainfall as a threat to their farm, which could be important for further research on agrivoltaics and the protection of crops from heavy rainfall. The modules also create shading that can protect against high levels of radiation. In addition, the rainwater could be collected for rainwater harvesting. The current irrigation system is largely based on river/stream water. This statement can also be supported by the relatively high average score of 4.17 for the opportunity 'potential use of rainwater for irrigation'. Rainwater harvesting could make the farms even more resilient to extreme weather events. This can also be supported by the opportunities 'improving the resilience' and the 'protection of the crops from extreme weather events'.

Considering the political goal of achieving a net-zero emissions economy by 2050, the results of farmer perceptions, and the feasibility of integrating renewable energies, it can be assumed that agrivoltaics can contribute to the expansion of renewable energies. By analysing the barriers investigated and the result of the support offers surveyed, the study would like to consider possibilities for the further focus of the approach.

In the survey, the support offer 'a test set-up to investigate the functionality' received the highest mean value. The use of a test set-up is particularly important as there is relatively little research on the topic of agrivoltaics in Seychelles; equally important is to investigate the suitability of certain crops as well as the effects on the microclimate, considering the specific location. Another possibility would be to start with large farms as trial sites for further research. Both options have the advantage that farmers can view the systems on-site and incorporate their experiences into their decision-making process. However, it is also important to take the other support offers into account as these also achieved high

mean values between 4.39 and 4.51 in the results. 'Financial support' is of great interest as the 'investment costs' are the biggest barrier. As previously mentioned, access to information and informational events is also an important support offer as this increases familiarity with the system and could therefore also influence the consideration. The support offers 'technical support options for repair and maintenance' and 'availability of trained officers' are also of great importance.

The evaluation shows that there is potential in the establishment of the new agrivoltaics technology in Seychelles as an exemplary country in the tropics, for example in the use of electricity or the use of irrigation systems. Further research is needed to investigate how exactly and in what way the use of agrivoltaics has the most potential for the farms, for example through a test set-up. This would allow agrivoltaics to be introduced in Seychelles in a targeted approach and ensuring that farmers can benefit from it as early as possible.

Conclusion and outlook

The study aimed to analyse the potential of agrivoltaics in Seychelles with a particular focus on the acceptance among farmers regarding this new technology. In this work, the focus was on open systems and agrivoltaics in the context of crop production. The data for the analysis was generated from 75 surveys collected through personal surveys with farmers on the main island of Mahé with the support of the Agriculture Department.

The results of the evaluation show that farmers are already open to and have shown a positive attitude towards agrivoltaics. In addition to various opportunities that the farmers see in the new technology, some barriers were also identified that the farmers perceive as obstacles to its implementation. Among the barriers, the costs and financing as well as the lack of specialized knowledge and experts in the field of agrivoltaics were named as the main barriers. Despite the barriers, a potential can be recognized, as the farmers see opportunities for their farms in the new technology, including the self-supply of electricity, the associated use of automated processes with the resulting reduction in the amount of work, as well as the cost savings and the possibility of using rainwater for irrigation. Moreover, for the assessment of the potential, the farm characteristics must be considered and the various design possibilities of agrivoltaics (e.g. overhead systems) must be considered.

The study has already taken the first step and created or deepened the awareness of the technology of agrivoltaics among certain stakeholders. Further measures can increase the presence of the topic and thereby also create more interest in the topic. These measures should be specifically selected. The results of this study can be used to consider specific points, such as to educate stakeholders in the special field of agrivoltaics. A start has already been made with the help of the workshop from the United Nations Conference on

Trade and Development regarding agrivoltaics in Seychelles. In the study, it became clear that the use of test set-ups would be beneficial in further promoting the implementation of agrivoltaics. This would allow testing of the suitability of agrivoltaics for the climatic conditions of a tropical island state and give farmers the opportunity to examine a sample project. The Anse Boileau Research Centre and the Seychelles Institute of Agriculture and Horticulture could be considered as possible research sites. This could combine research and training and create knowledge on the subject of agrivoltaics in tropical climates. However, it should be recognized that the tropics consist of a large number of countries with different topographical and climatic conditions. In the specific situation of Seychelles, there is also a need for further research into, for example, financing concepts, the suitability of specific crops and the specific design of agrivoltaics.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by a fellowship of the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD) and was carried out in cooperation with the Department of Environment at the University of Seychelles and with the help of the Department of Agriculture. The authors would like to thank all the above for their support.

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